

2ND DIAMOND OPEN ACCESS CONFERENCE REPORT

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'2nd Diamond Access Conference Report'

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Lead Author: Bregt Saenen (Science Europe)
Co-authors: Zoé Ancion (ANR), Lidia Borrell-Damián (Science Europe), Pierre Mounier (OPERAS), David Oliva Uribe (Science Europe/EUMex-Connect), Nora Papp-Le Roy (cOAlition S), Johan Rooryck (cOAlition S)

Design: Iwan Groeneveld (Science Europe)

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For further information, please contact the Science Europe Office at office@scienceeurope.org

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Table of Contents

Foreword	4
Introduction	6
Report of Proceedings	7
Diamond Scholarly Communication Infrastructure	7
Policy Development	8
Sustainability and Funding of Diamond Open Access	10
Governance and Global Federation	11
Research Evaluation and Recognition	12
The Way Forward	14
Annex – Community Webinar Event Report	16

Foreword

by **Thierry Damerval, President and CEO of the French National Research Agency**

The first Global Summit on Diamond Open Access brought together the worldwide community of researchers, editors, universities, research-performing organisations, academic libraries, learned societies, publishers, funders and policy makers engaged in strengthening the Diamond Open Access ecosystem. This hybrid and multilingual event gathered nearly 700 people representing 457 institutions from 75 countries in North America, Latin America and the Caribbean, Africa, Europe and Asia.

As a Governing Board member of Science Europe, the representative organisation of public research funding and performing organisations in Europe, I was very honoured to be part of this first edition. Our organisation has been at the forefront of collaborative efforts to unite the scientific research sector around common goals, facilitating a change in the way we approach open science and equitable research practices.

In recent years, we have witnessed remarkable developments in the public research sector. Its ambitions have grown exponentially, taking forward positive research cultures and driving the transition to equitable open science. It is Science Europe's privilege to be an advocate for change. We could highlight Science Europe support with seed funding for a seminal study on Diamond Open Access Journals in 2021. Science Europe joined hands with OPERAS, cOAlition S and ANR to draw up the Action Plan for Diamond Open Access. It demonstrates the collaborative spirit that drives our community and underlines our commitment to making immediate and equitable open access a reality for all.

The summit was an important moment for science and co-operation. It was the occasion to stress the need to support equitable access to scholarly publishing and reading with a focus on the quality of the content rather than on the publishing venue. This is part of the current global discussion particularly in the context of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). We have collectively agreed

on the need to support existing and new Diamond OA journals, repositories, and platforms. Therefore, during the conclusions of the summit it was announced that a Global Federation for Diamond Open Access would be created. UNESCO has offered to contribute to this federation and to host its secretariat. The French Ministry of Higher Education and Research has also announced its support.

The summit hosted the 2nd Diamond Open Access Conference which brought together signatories to the Action Plan for Diamond Open Access to further develop efficiency, quality standards, capacity building and sustainability. As of today, more than 160 institutions from across the globe have endorsed the Action Plan. In line with this plan and political statements such as the EU Council Conclusions on High Quality, Transparent, Open, Trustworthy, and Equitable Scholarly Publishing and the second French National Plan for Open Science, ANR announced its strong support in Toluca. With funding of €250K for the launch of the European Diamond Capacity Hub, it aims to facilitate access to the necessary resources for all those managing diamond OA publications, venues, and initiatives in Europe in collaboration with other regional Capacity hubs of the Global Federation. This financial support is in addition to the €850k that ANR has already allocated to the French National Fund for Open Science in support of Diamond projects. The French National Centre for Scientific Research has also announced its support for the European Capacity Hub.

This consensus extends to national policies and the policies of Science Europe's member organisations, amplifying the impact of our collective efforts. To strengthen this effort, I invite funders and research institutions to join this global movement to support bibliodiversity and equitable scholarly publishing.

– Thierry Damerval
*President and CEO of the
French National Research Agency*

Introduction

This is the event report for the [2nd Diamond Open Access Conference](#), a global gathering where stakeholders were able to explore, discuss, and share insights on the Diamond Open Access scholarly communication ecosystem. The event was organised on 25–26 October 2023 in Toluca, Mexico by Science Europe, cOAlition S, OPERAS, and the French National Research Agency (ANR).

The Conference was part of the [Global Summit on Diamond Open Access](#), which took place on 23–27 October 2023 – a week-long series of events that highlighted the pivotal role of Diamond Open Access in scholarly communication. Other events that were part of the Global Summit include the [4th Redalyc Conference of Journal Editors](#) and the [2nd AmeliCA meeting](#). The events were preceded and followed by an [opening and closing ceremony](#).

The Global Summit brought together a broad range of global participants, including researchers, editors, universities, research funding and performing organisations, academic libraries, learned societies, and policy makers. It reached 688 participants across 75 countries. Its hybrid nature, encompassing both in-person and virtual participation, ensured that a global audience could engage in the discussion, making it a truly inclusive and accessible event.

The closing ceremony of the Global Summit saw the launch of the '[Global Summit on Diamond Open Access Conclusions and Way Forward](#)' (Oct 2023). These conclusions emphasise global engagement and exchange as the way forward, with the organising partners reinforcing their commitment to this approach.

The Conference focused specifically on five key elements of Diamond Open Access: infrastructure, policy development, governance, research evaluation and recognition, and sustainability.

This event report reflects the Conference's mission, as part of the Global Summit, to showcase good practices and policies from various corners of the globe, offering attendees a comprehensive perspective on the role of Diamond Open Access in scholarly communication worldwide. Following the [first conference](#) that took place on 19–20 September 2022 in Zadar, Croatia, these events, together with regular community webinars, bring together a fast-growing community centred on the '[Action Plan for Diamond Open Access](#)'. Launched by Science Europe, cOAlition S, OPERAS, and ANR in March 2022, the Action Plan has been endorsed by more than 300 organisations and individuals from across the public research sector. This publication also includes, in Annex 1, a report of the community webinar that was held online on 18 September 2023, where this community of endorsers met to discuss their views in preparation for the Global Summit.

The Action Plan that grew out of '[The Diamond Open Access Journals Study](#)' (March 2021) and is currently being developed further by the Horizon Europe project '[Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication](#)' (DIAMAS). Having identified the fragmentation of the diamond open access ecosystem, this project aims to facilitate cohesion and alignment by formulating community-led recommendations and guidelines for institutional leaders, research funders, sponsors, and donors, and policy makers in Europe.

Report of Proceedings

Participants, speakers, and moderators were welcomed to the 2nd Diamond Open Access Conference by **Thierry Damerval** (Governing Board Member of Science Europe, and President & CEO of the French National Research Agency (ANR)), followed by a plenary introduction that reflected on the progress made so far, and how we can chart a path forward. **Arianna Becerril-García** (Executive Director of Redalyc/AmeliCA) and **Lidia Borrell-Damián** (Secretary General of Science Europe) discussed the remarkable increase in political support and engagement from the public sector in diamond scholarly communication. This set the stage for the Conference, highlighting the journey undertaken so far and providing a glimpse into the path that lies ahead.

Diamond Scholarly Communication Infrastructure

How do we develop a roadmap that can lead us towards a global diamond scholarly communication infrastructure? In other words, how can we make effective policy decisions and sound investments to strengthen Diamond scholarly communication worldwide? A plenary workshop moderated by Lidia Borrell-Damián brought together speakers and participants in Toluca and online to delve into these questions.

The stage was set by **Johan Rooryck** (Executive Director of cOAlition S and Editor-in-chief of 'Glossa: a journal of general linguistics') and **Pierre Mounier** (Co-Coordinator of OPERAS). Together they presented their vision to make a reality one of the key recommendations from '[The OA Diamond Journals Study](#)' (March 2021) and the '[Action Plan for Diamond Open Access](#)' (March 2022): a Diamond Capacity Hub that provides technical, financial, legal, governance, and training services and resources at different levels to diamond journals, editors, repositories, and platforms. They invited participants to envision with them a globally federated scholarly communication infrastructure operating at four different levels, including regional capacity hubs, providing tailored support globally, regionally, nationally and locally, and at journal level. The paper that resulted from this presentation is available at thd.hypotheses.org/296.

Their vision for a globally federated infrastructure is not a castle in the sky, but one that builds upon the many governance and funding models, services and tools that already exist and are actively being developed and implemented worldwide. To learn from all these examples, the plenary workshop continued with speakers presenting their work to inspire and invite further discussion.

Governance models for a Diamond scholarly communication infrastructure were explored by **Kamran Naim** (Open Science Section Leader at the European Organization for Nuclear Research, CERN) presenting the [Sponsoring Consortium for Open Access Publishing in Particle Physics](#) (SCOAP³), **Guy Cochrane** (Executive Director of the Global Biodata Coalition, GBC) presenting the [Global Biodata Coalition](#), and **Juan Pablo Alperin** (Co-Scientific Director of the Public Knowledge Project, PKP) presenting the [Public Knowledge Project](#).

Financing models for a Diamond scholarly communication infrastructure were explored by four invited speakers. **Remya Haridasan** (Scientist at Office of the Principal Scientific Adviser to the Government of India) presented the current state of diamond open access journals in India. **Giannis Tsakonias** (Vice President of LIBER Europe and Director of the Library & Information Center, University of Patras, Greece) offered insights on the comprehensive role of research libraries in providing financial and other support to the research communities they serve. **Joanna Ball** (Managing Director of the Directory of Open Access Journals, DOAJ) presented the crowdfunding and collective action model that lies at the heart of the [Directory of Open Access Journals](#), specifically noting the challenge of funding initiatives with an international outlook. Finally, **Melissa Hagemann** (Director of the Budapest Open Access Initiative) presented the [Budapest Open Access Initiative](#) which prioritises community-driven models over commercial ones. She also specifically noted the challenge of replicating at global level the best practices found at regional and national level.

How do we move forward with a global diamond scholarly communication infrastructure? Participants in Toluca and online were invited to add their own perspectives and further unpack those of the speakers in a plenary discussion moderated by **Ana Persic** (Programme Specialist for Science Policy and Partnerships at the Division of Science Policy and Capacity Building, UNESCO).

The discussion illustrated the broad range of perspectives on this central question, coming from representatives working in the Americas, Africa, Asia, Europe, and, not least, globally. However, despite their diverse backgrounds, common threads could be identified among the interventions. *“How do we avoid commercial capture of diamond open access initiatives?”*, asked one concerned participant. Others readily admitted sharing this concern and exchanged ideas on how to avoid this in the future. A key suggestion was to ensure diamond open access journals, repositories, and platforms are owned and governed by the academic community. A future Diamond Capacity Hub (cf. infra) could support initiatives in building legal and governance frameworks toward this goal.

Policy Development

Policy development at both national and regional levels is crucial to bolster the diamond open access model in scholarly communication. This plenary session moderated by **Martine Garnier-Rizet** (Head of Digital Strategy and Data Directorate at the French National Research Agency, ANR) invited speakers and participants to discuss policies being developed worldwide and how different levels can work together to build a robust framework.

Michael Arentoft (Head of Unit Open Science at the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European Commission) joined online to speak in favour of a high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing system that places the researchers at its centre. He presented the framework conditions that are necessary for scholarly publishing to change and the way forward in terms of building capacities underlined in the [Conclusions of the Council of the European Union](#) published in May 2023. Regarding [Open Research Europe](#) (ORE), Michael stressed the need of making the platform a more collective endeavour, that could be collectively driven, owned and supported by funders and research institutions. Now the objective is to continue to emphasise on a strong involvement of the research community with the ambition of creating an environment where research communities can find their home.

Karina Batthyány (Executive Secretary of CLACSO) pointed out several political priorities to strengthen Diamond Open Access. The first one is to regain community control over the research assessment and to include indicators from the regional and international quality journal indexing services such as [Latindex](#), [Redalyc](#), [Scielo](#) or [DOAJ](#). Multilingualism as a means of disseminating should also be promoted. Finally, international co-operation should be strengthened with initiatives from all regions of the world. However, Karina drew attention to the fact that the 'globalisation' of initiatives born in the southern regions must not erase the regional actors, but rather make them decision makers.

Marin Dacos (National Open Science Coordinator at the French Ministry of Higher Education, Research, and Innovation) presented the open science policy in France and the actions carried out to support Diamond Open Access. In France and in Europe, the aim is now to rebalance the scientific publishing landscape. Gold APC journals have benefited from a large amount of funding, unlike Diamond journals. Therefore, Marin stressed the importance of a plurality of publishing venues including funding for diamond initiatives. Finally, in order to avoid the 'free rider' phenomenon (using infrastructures without financing them), he called for a sustainable and shared funding for diamond infrastructures on an international scale through initiatives such as SCOSS.

Martin Halbert (Science Advisor for Public Access at the National Science Foundation (NSF), US) pointed out that mobilisation towards diamond open access in the United States lags behind Latin America and Europe. Nevertheless, the US federated funding agencies acknowledge the increasingly unreasonable cost that scientists are regularly encountering in publishing their findings arising from federal grants. Therefore, the question of equity and efficiency which are raised by high APCs needs to be addressed. This awareness necessitates the call for new models like diamond open access. Martin stressed that as a result of [the Nelson Memo](#), all US research funding agencies are actively updating their policies and it is an opportune time to seek national and international alignment.

Kazuhiro Hayashi (Director of Research Unit for Data Application at the National Institute of Science and Technology Policy, Japan) introduced his organisation's open access policy and announced that following the G7 Summit that took place in Hiroshima last May, Japan will soon formulate a national policy to promote immediate open access to publicly funded scholar publishing and scientific data associated to publications. Kazuhiro also presented [J-Stage](#), a platform for scholarly publications developed and managed by the Japan Science and Technology Agency for Japan's academic societies as a potential Diamond Open Access platform. To strengthen this kind of platform, he called for a dialogue between international stakeholders for behaviour change, as researchers still too often choose international commercial publishers over Diamond journals and platforms to disseminate their publications.

Martine Garnier-Rizet concluded the session with panellists from Latin America and the Caribbean, North America, Asia and Europe, who presented the policies already developed or being developed to strengthen diamond open access. She highlighted key elements such as shared funding at the international level to support global initiatives and to have a systemic impact, support skills and capacity building as well as supporting infrastructures in the long-term.

Sustainability and Funding of Diamond Open Access

Capacity building and sustainable financing are key pillars for the future development of diamond open access. A plenary session moderated by **Eurico Wongo Gungula** (Rector of the Universidade Óscar Ribas (UOR), Angola) invited speakers and participants to discuss how we can further strengthen, sustain, and fund the Diamond Open Access scholarly communication model.

Jo Havemann (Open Science Communication Consultant and Trainer at AfricArXiv) presented [AfricArXiv](#) and its ambition to make African research discoverable. It relies on mixed revenue streams to gather funding for its work, including sources such as donations, prizes, grants, membership fees, course fees, and consultation services. Jo pointed to the support AfricArXiv provides to Diamond Open Access in Africa, which happens through both university presses and African journals.

Catherine Mitchell (Director of Publishing, Archives, and Digitization at the California Digital Library, University of California, US) reflected on the experience of [eScholarship](#), the open access publishing platform subsidised by the University of California that plays an important role as an equitable diamond open access publisher focussed on scholar-led journals that align with the values of the university, rather than commercial interests. Catherine called upon the diamond open access community to make the often invisible labour visible, rather than hiding the human and financial costs of Diamond Open Access behind volunteers with no resources beyond their commitment.

Ross Mounce (Director Open Access Programmes at Arcadia) presented the comprehensive financial support offered by [Arcadia](#) for open access initiatives, tools, and infrastructures. Although noting that sustainability should be understood beyond purely financial terms, Ross highlighted the rich potential of endowments and the common sense of long-term grants as funding models that could establish diamond open access initiatives on a more sustainable financial footing.

Vanessa Proudman (Director of SPARC Europe, and Executive Group Chair of the Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services, SCOSS) raised the connection between research funders and open research infrastructures that is made by the SCOSS. SCOSS makes this connection to ensure not-for-profit services can continue and are placed on a more secure financial footing. Vanessa pointed out that the financial precarity of many infrastructures creates the risk that their services will stagnate, downsize, disappear behind paywalls, or lose their autonomy. SCOSS announced that it would make Diamond Open Access one of its priority areas for funding for its next call.

Giulia Malaguarnera (Board Member and former Secretary of the Marie Curie Alumni Association, MCAA, and Outreach and Engagement Officer at OpenAIRE) connected the discussion on sustainability to research careers, especially those of early-stage researchers represented by the [Marie Curie Alumni Association](#). Highlighting an essential point, Giulia pointed out that a research system built on precarious careers is not a sustainable system at all. Challenges in the diamond open access scholarly communication models are also represented by the necessity to outreach the research community of interest to facilitate the researchers' career development; particularly, in terms of collaboration and stabilisation.

Jeroen Sondervan (Programme Leader Open Scholarly Communication at Open Science NL, the Netherlands) provided reflections on the challenges and opportunities to promote diamond open access in the Netherlands. Taking a European outlook, he noted that research assessment reform organised through the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#) opens the way towards a more sustainable research system and hopefully a growing uptake of diamond open access. Jeroen discussed the financial support provided by both the Dutch Research Council (NWO) and the ten-year initiative [Open Science NL](#) (embedded in NWO) for diamond open access, noting this will be expanded in the near future. At the same time, he pointed out that Europe should not reinvent the wheel, with well-functioning examples such as [Redalyc](#) existing in other world regions.

Heather Joseph (Executive Director of SPARC) introduced [SPARC's](#) belief that sharing knowledge is a human right, one that everyone should be able to access, contribute to, and benefit from. SPARC as an organisation is a catalyst for action towards this goal. Delving into funding models, Heather presented to the audience the continuum ranging from market transactions (hybrid, and gold APC/BPC) to collective support (non-APC/BPC conditional, collective, and subsidy models).

Nokuthula Mchunu (Deputy Director of the African Open Science Platform, AOSP and National Research Foundation, South Africa) introduced the co-ordinating role of the [African Open Science Platform](#). While other actors in the African continent can develop and implement the ecosystem to make open access a reality, AOSP is working to co-ordinate these efforts and organise them through a series of regional hubs. Her call was for partnership of equals between the Global North and South, where the latter has a voice in the path forward despite its comparative financial precarity.

The presentations were followed by a moderated question-and-answer session. Participants in Toluca and online picked up on various elements introduced by the speakers, specifically the different funding models that are being explored and utilised. Together with the speakers, participants engaged in a broader reflection on the shape of a sustainable not-for-profit ecosystem, considering the different options to move forward with a sustainable and well-funded diamond open access scholarly communication system. Consistent regular funding was pointed out as key to provide stability. Nations were encouraged to set up national Open Science funds, as seen in France or the Netherlands, in addition to libraries or institutions to have open access funds of their own. Research funders were invited to aim for longer grant durations to help keep project application costs down. Furthermore, a global campaign could encourage to reduce the spend on non-equitable publishing models.

Governance and Global Federation

How do we build a globally federated Diamond Open Access ecosystem? The aim of this panel was to discuss the governance of this ecosystem with respect for its diversity and decentralised nature, and what is to be gained from alignment. The session was moderated by **Ana Persic** (Program Specialist for Science Policy and Partnerships at the Division of Science Policy and Capacity Building, UNESCO).

Regarding governance, **Sharla Lair** (Senior Strategist Open Access & Scholarly Communication Initiatives at Lyrasis) emphasised the need to move from isolated to collective and connected impact and presented five conditions for alignment inspired from the [Strive programme](#): a common agenda, a shared measurement

system, mutually reinforcing activities, a continuous communication, and a backbone support organisation. If the Global Federated Network for Diamond Open Access endorses these principles, it would enable a more equitable distribution, allow more voices to be heard in the research communication and provide the content of journals and books available to all, including to citizens.

Tanja Niemann (Executive Director of Érudit, and co-founder of Coalition Publica) suggested using the co-operative model, which promotes owned, controlled and run people-centred enterprises as an inspiration to build a global federation of Diamond Open Access. These co-operatives should also be associated with other core values such as inclusiveness and multilingualism. The diversity of the national contexts that could create fragility and complexity need to be addressed in the future architecture of the Global Federation.

Antonio Sánchez Pereyra (SciELO) presented the open science infrastructure SciELO and the SciELO network, a federation of 16 countries which support open access research communication. Despite the financial and technical inequalities between countries, SciELO has managed to co-ordinate and make collective decisions thanks to its 25 years of experience in weaving the network. In recent years, an increasing number of journals indexed in SciELO have begun to charge publication fees to partially or totally finance their operation. Antonio mentioned that SciELO allows a Contribution to Cost of Publication (CCP) if they are a necessity for the journal to survive.

Mochammad Tanzil Multazam (Head of Library at the Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo, Indonesia) shared a presentation entitled 'Govern Diamond Open Access: Indonesia Case' which highlighted the exponential growth of open access journals in Indonesia, featuring around 20,000 journals due to the strong support of the Indonesian Government for open science. Mochammad also presented the Indonesian Journal Volunteer Association, which gathers more than 700 volunteers committed to help publishers improve their skills.

After looking back at the highlights of each presentation, **Johan Rooryck** (Executive Director of cOAlition S, and Editor-in-chief of 'Glossa: a journal of general linguistics') and the speakers engaged in a broader reflection on a number of principles for the governance of the Global Federation including inclusiveness, multilingualism, diversity and community-drivenness.

Research Evaluation and Recognition

This joint panel between the Redalyc editors' meetings and the 2nd Diamond Open Access Conference was moderated by **Sylvie Rousset** (Steering Board member at CoARA, and Director of the Scientific and Technical Information Department, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), France). Sylvie Rousset set the stage by affirming that there was an international consensus to change assessment criteria to take into account diamond open access journals.

Lidia Borrell-Damián (Secretary General of Science Europe, and representative of CoARA) introduced the global initiative created in 2022 to reform research assessment, CoARA. CoARA builds on a series of precursory initiatives in the field of research assessment and aims to bring change along 4 main axes:

- ◆ Recognition of wider diversity of research outcomes
- ◆ Qualitative assessment of research outputs

- ♦ Moving away from quantitative journal metrics
- ♦ Moving away from university rankings

LAC institutions were encouraged to join the global initiative.

Pilar Rico-Castro (Head of the Open Science, Repositories, and Academica Journals Unit at the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology, FECYT) spoke about the role of national research evaluation agencies in defending diamond open access journals and making them recognised in research assessment. She stressed that we should not transfer to third-party commercial service providers what we mean by quality in research, but that decisions about quality should be in the hands of the research community, and represent a public good.

Laura Rovelli (Coordinator at the Latin American Forum for Research Assessment (FOLEC) of the Latin American Council of Social Sciences (CLACSO)), presented the example in the Latin-American region of CLACSO-FOLEC in reforming research assessment.

In January 2022, CLACSO-FOLEC adopted a [Declaration of Principles regarding New Research Assessment Towards a Socially Relevant Science in Latin America and the Caribbean](#), which emphasises the need to regain control of the academic and research community over the assessment processes and indicators. The indicators of published output used in the assessment processes should include indicators produced by regional indexing services as well as indicators from national indexes of quality journals, and support multilingualism and cultural diversity. The countries in the region are putting in place assessment reforms that are in line with the aims of Diamond Open Access, such as incentivising non-commercial models, promoting Diamond Open Access publishing venues for publicly funded research, and recognition for peer review and editorial work in research assessment.

Ellen Tise (Senior Director Library and Information Services at the University of Stellenbosch, South Africa) joined online and presented the situation in South Africa, which does not have a formal Research Assessment (RA) framework, but is based on traditional criteria: outputs, number of publications, citations, high-impact journals, and so on.

Many institutions and agencies do support open access through mandates or repositories. Why do we want to take OA into account in RA? Is it an end in itself, or a means to an end? Open Science in itself is a radical departure from traditional research and RA. Problems with Open Science include the fact that it disadvantages researchers from the Global South and thus reinforces the 'publish or perish' pressure.

She said that we need to move away from the conservatism that supports senior academics and work with early-career researchers to incentivise Open Science. A cultural change is needed. Diamond Open Access has to be incorporated into RA and should be incentivised through the following elements:

- ♦ Government and funder mandates that require that publicly funded research must be published in open access
- ♦ Universities' OA repositories
- ♦ Incentives for researchers who publish in Diamond Open Access venues
- ♦ Development of a robust peer review and quality assurance system
- ♦ Alternative research metrics and international awards for OA publishing (e.g. by UNESCO or the International Science Council)

Sheila Godínez Larios (Research coordinator at Sistema de Información Científica Redalyc, México) presented the methodology for assessing diamond open access at Redalyc, based on the use of over 100 indicators developed by Redalyc to assess how research is conducted. These indicators allow to create precise and varied 'cartographies of knowledge' of non-commercial scientific publishing world-wide and show the direction of collaborations within regions and with the 'mainstream' European scientific community. Findings show that in the Diamond Open Access sector, collaborations tend to be more symmetrical. Redalyc and Clacso produced two reports about the methodology to assess Diamond Open Access and regarding open access publishing in Redalyc: [Metodología para la evaluación de la ciencia en acceso abierto digital diamante](#) and [La producción científica de México en revistas de acceso abierto digital diamante en Redalyc](#).

Fernanda Beigel (Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas, Argentina) stressed in a video message that research assessment must discuss not merely indexation or impact but the academic quality of journals, and that the way that quality is decided is not equitable. New methods of assessment have to be developed that are more balanced, globally applied, but also locally relevant. Research assessment for Diamond Open Access has to favour collaboration and open science.

The Way Forward

The Diamond Open Access community took a big step forward during the 2nd Diamond Open Access Conference. As part of the Global Summit, the global outlook of this community was made into a reality by highlighting initiatives from across the world. Looking forward, the '[Global Summit on Diamond Open Access Conclusions and Way Forward](#)' (October 2023) emphasised global engagement and exchange as the way forward, with the organising partners reinforcing their commitment to this approach.

In 2024, this global outlook will be taken forward with the establishment of a Global Federation for Diamond Open Access, hosted by UNESCO. The four-level [proposed infrastructure](#) co-ordinated by the Global Federation will aim at providing resources and services to diamond open access communities worldwide to strengthen their role in scholarly communication. It will be a global infrastructure serving communities worldwide, while operating as a distributed system that aligns diverse communities to achieve shared goals.

The infrastructure will take the shape of a four-level federation, with each level having its own responsibilities to achieve the shared goal of strengthening diamond open access as a leading scholarly communication model. These levels and their responsibilities are taking shape through discussions with diamond open access communities and other stakeholders in the research landscape. We invite you to come forward and join this discussion.

ANNEX

Community Webinar Event Report

On 18 September 2023, the Diamond Action Plan Community met online to discuss various facets of a declaration on diamond open access, with an eye to preparing the Diamond Summit held from 23–27 October in Toluca, Mexico. What follows is a synthesis of the discussion that took place. It is followed by a call to action to all stakeholders to inform us how they can help co-create Diamond Open Access infrastructure.

The discussion on diamond open access is fast-evolving. This webinar represents a key moment in the community's thinking about the way forward. The ideas that were first discussed during this event, were further developed during the Global Summit in late October 2023.

1. Preamble

Diamond Open Access is a community-driven scholarly communication model. It allows research outputs to be immediately available via an open license without charging fees to authors or readers. It is equitable by nature and design. It thus facilitates all contributors' equal participation in knowledge creation, dissemination, reuse, and preservation. Diamond Open Access fosters the right of everyone to have access to the benefits of scientific progress and its applications.

Diamond Open Access places the autonomy and sovereignty of academic communities at the centre of scholarly communication. Scholarly communities should direct and own the publication and dissemination of research outputs. As a result, Diamond Open Access journals, books, repositories, and platforms are ideally placed to counterbalance extractive commercial practices that aim at capturing economic value in the scholarly communication system and lock researchers in commercial dependencies.

In many global regions and disciplines, Diamond Open Access has proven to be a vibrant, sustainable, and well-functioning publishing model that serves its scholarly communities with creative and novel approaches for organising the scholarly discussion. The interaction between Diamond Open Access and other scholarly communication models, notably including commercial publishing, is diverse across disciplines, communities, and regions of the world. In Latin America, the focus is on non-commercial publishing, with a strong stance against the commodification of knowledge. In other parts of the world, Diamond Open Access attempts to negotiate a new compact with the commercial sector, distinguishing between control of content-related elements by the scholarly community, and service-related elements that can be contracted with commercial service providers. We believe there is room for various Diamond Open Access pathways that converge towards shared knowledge without financial or legal barriers and in line with principles of quality, efficiency, equity, and bibliodiversity.

Diamond Open Access allows for a more transparent accounting of resources allocated to academic publishing, and provides equitable and inclusive access to research results for scholars and citizens alike. Therefore, it is a priority to support the strengthening of the Diamond Open Access ecosystem for the public research community working in all knowledge disciplines worldwide.

2. Facets of Diamond Open Access

Equity

Diamond Open Access is equitable by nature and design: it does not charge fees to either authors or readers. As such, it aims at reducing inequities between researchers and readers, and tries to avoid the systematic exclusion of historically marginalised communities and regions. Participation is a constitutive element of the Diamond Open Access scholarly communication model: without it there is no equity.

Knowledge as a public good

Research results and other outputs of scholarly discussion are a public good. As such, they are part of the heritage of humanity. Diamond Open Access champions the principle that scholarly outputs should be immediately accessible to all without embargo, openly licensed, and without financial or other barriers for authors and readers. The copyright to publicly funded research publications should be retained by the author(s) and/or public institution that funded the knowledge. The copyright to publicly funded knowledge should not be transferred to commercial entities.

This enables the research community, policymakers, and the general public to immediately and openly access, reuse, and build upon scholarly knowledge. Unrestricted access to knowledge will greatly foster research progress in disciplinary, multidisciplinary, and interdisciplinary research. Support for new and existing Diamond Open Access journals, books, repositories, and platforms globally can significantly lower barriers to accessing and disseminating publicly-funded research.

Community-driven

Diamond Open Access ensures that academic communities are at the centre of scholarly communication. Scholarly communities control and drive all content-related elements of scholarly communication: quality assurance, editorial guidelines and decisions, and best practices. The quality of the content of research publications and platforms is ensured by scholars themselves. Service-related aspects of scholarly communication – e.g. submission systems, copy-editing, typesetting, digital preservation – can be contracted with commercial service providers. Such contracts should be transparent, competitive, time-delimited, open for negotiation, and free of any lock-in mechanisms or non-disclosure agreements. All data shared with or collected by service providers remains in the ownership of the scholarly community, and must be digitally transportable to another digital tool or platform without additional fees. The distinction between content-related and service-related aspects of academic publishing ensures that

knowledge remains a public good, and allows for a new and properly balanced public-private partnership between academic communities and commercial service providers.

Diversity

Diversity is the recognition of the plurality of voices as well as economic, political, societal and cultural contexts. Its preservation is one of the conditions for globalisation, democratic access to research and for the common good. Multilingualism is a constitutive part of diversity.

The commitment to build a global community of knowledge implies the recognition, support and understanding of the different contexts in which knowledge and publications are generated. Global, regional, national and local diversity should be identified, valued and supported. A global village includes a diversity and multiplicity of Diamond Open Access publisher organisations and journal communities.

Diamond Open Access journals, books, and platforms serve a wide diversity of communities and they are collaborative, multilingual and culturally diverse. Diamond Open Access publications, like other actors in scholarly publishing, make use of rigorous procedures of scientific quality assurance to guarantee the scientific and editorial quality of the content they publish. Likewise, Diamond Open Access generates responsible, transparent, open and innovative ways to assess research aimed at building community and consolidating the purpose of knowledge: responding to the needs of society. The cultural and linguistic multiplicity of Diamond Open Access communities testify to its rich bibliodiversity. Diamond Open Access journals, books, repositories, and platforms represent community-driven and academic-led publishing initiatives. Diamond Open Access is ultimately an instrument to achieve equitable, diverse, inclusive, and fair scholarly communication.

We acknowledge that Diamond Open Access journals, books, repositories, and platforms can be as diverse as required by the needs of the different research disciplines and epistemic traditions. Diamond Open Access is driven by the priorities of the scholarly community. Different stakeholders in various world regions and countries possess varying capacities to adopt and implement Diamond Open Access practices. Therefore, we recognise the importance of tailoring local actions along the global principles and roadmap to leverage the opportunities of diamond open access as the foremost model for scholarly communication within academic standards.

Transitioning to Diamond

A large amount of public funding is already allocated to scholarly publishing. Academic libraries pay commercial publishers for access to knowledge produced by their own researchers, creating inefficiencies and inequities in the process. Although additional initial funding will be needed to reinforce Diamond Open Access, we believe that library funds should be gradually redirected towards strengthening Diamond Open Access, in the interest of a more cost-efficient and more equitable scholarly communication system. We will work with all parties involved, but the focus has to be on full and immediate access with an open license, and the best possible dissemination of knowledge, not on publishers' profits or the right to be able to continue to operate outdated business models and practices.

Research assessment and recognition

The scientific community worldwide is mobilising to reform research assessment systems. Research assessment tools and practices should be owned and driven by the academic community.

We encourage the adoption of assessment practices that recognise the quality of scientific works irrespective of the venues where they are published, recognise a broader diversity of contributions and outputs of researchers, including data sets, software development, and public engagement. They should encompass a broad range of scholarly activities and impact, giving due consideration to the societal value of research.

In this context, particular attention should go to rewarding the currently invisible and unrewarded work of Diamond Open Access editors, reviewers, production managers, and platform technicians. The work of editors and reviewers is a foundational contribution to research, it should be recognized as such.

Diamond Open Access should be recognised in research practices, researcher evaluation systems, Open Access policies. The contributions to diamond open access made by researchers, organisations, institutions, journals, book publishers, and platforms should be identified and recognized when evaluating the efforts of each stakeholder towards the adoption and consolidation of Open Access, in particular, and Open Science, in general.

Multi-level co-operation

We commit to fostering partnerships among stakeholders, including universities, research organisations, funding bodies, research libraries, academic societies, research infrastructures, publishing service providers, researchers at all stages of their careers, and policymakers, to develop shared strategies, initiatives, and infrastructure that support the transition to Diamond Open Access. Co-ordinated local, regional, and global efforts are necessary to advance Diamond Open Access.

3. Roadmap towards Diamond Open Access: A Call to Action

A Distributed and Federated Infrastructure

We envision a Diamond Open Access infrastructure that is distributed and federated. We will create a network of national Diamond Capacity Centres and Regional Capacity Hubs similar to Redalyc-Amelica and SciELO at the national, regional and global levels. This federated structure acknowledges the critical role of regional and national initiatives in shaping the implementation of Diamond Open Access.

The Regional Diamond Capacity Hubs will support the exchange and alignment of best practices, guidelines, and quality standards such as those developed in the context of the DIAMAS project (EQSIP); as well as the development of local solutions that address specific needs and challenges faced by different disciplines, languages, and regions. The Diamond Capacity Hubs will help new and existing Diamond Open Access journals to align their operations with accepted quality standards, reinforce their governance, and ensure their long-term sustainability.

The governance of the Capacity Centres will consist of representatives of:

1. funders (*financial or in-kind support by funding agencies and universities*)
2. providers (*university presses and libraries, scholarly societies, non-profit organisations*)
3. Diamond journals
4. national/local Diamond Capacity Centres

Co-creating Diamond Infrastructure

A roadmap towards Diamond Open Access should be developed that will function as a tool to design and create a strongly federated Diamond Open Access infrastructure. This text is meant as a call to action for all stakeholders to provide us with a (brief) description of how they see their role in and contribution to a Diamond Open Access infrastructure that is governed and controlled by the academic community.

For example, university libraries and presses can describe how their operations contribute to Diamond Open Access. Universities and research organisations can contribute an inventory of those researchers who work as editors of Diamond Open Access journals. This will provide us with precious bottom-up information about the building blocks of the organically federated Diamond Open Access infrastructure we envision.

We provide further indications below of what various academic stakeholders can do to contribute to Diamond Open Access:

- ◆ Funding agencies and governments can develop supportive policy frameworks and provide financial support for the national, regional, and global Diamond Capacity Centres.
- ◆ Universities and their organisations can promote a better understanding of the global diamond publishing landscape.
- ◆ All stakeholders can examine how they can contribute to Diamond Open Access technical, social, and legal infrastructures: financial and in-kind support for capacity centres, local platforms, journals, and editors.
- ◆ Universities and university libraries can establish frameworks, policies, rewards and incentives, mutual learning exercises, and peer exchanges in order to enable the academic community to move away from the existing system, and redirect funds that are currently tied up in payments for commercial publishing.
- ◆ Funding agencies and ministries can contribute to establishing a global federation for Diamond Open Access.
- ◆ Universities can reform research assessment by adopting global practices and tools that are owned and controlled by the academic community, and by rewarding Diamond Open Access editors, reviewers and technicians locally.
- ◆ Scholarly society and non-profit disciplinary organisations can create and strengthen existing Diamond Open Access journals.
- ◆ Existing Diamond Open Access infrastructures can further align their practices, training modules, and collaborate on the interoperability of their platforms.

- ◆ Creating new Diamond Open Access journals in scholarly disciplines that lack them.
- ◆ Universities and research performing organisations can encourage researchers in all disciplines to publish in Diamond Open Access journals and appropriately reward that practice.

